

LESSON: Situation-specific emotion training for autism spectrum disorder children

T. Abdulbaki Alshirbaji^{1,2*}, H. Arabian¹, V. Wunsch³, V. Wagner-Hartl^{1,3}, and K. Moeller¹

¹ Institute of Technical Medicine (ITeM), Furtwangen University, 78054 Villingen-Schwenningen, Germany

² Innovation Center Computer Assisted Surgery (ICCAS), University of Leipzig, 04103 Leipzig, Germany

³ Department of Industrial Technologies, Campus Tuttlingen Furtwangen University, 78532 Tuttlingen, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: Tamer.AbdulbakiAlshirbaji@hs-furtwangen.de

Abstract: This project introduces an innovative system to situation-specific emotion training for children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) using a virtual reality (VR) system. Addressing the challenges associated with social communication and emotional recognition in ASD, this project aims to develop a VR game that trains ASD children to recognize and express emotions through interactive simulations of everyday situations. Two preliminary phases are implemented to help ASD subjects better understanding and developing emotions. These training phases are 'mimic training' to mimic avatar expressions and 'mirror training' to observe personal expressions. The system recognises and analyses responses and expressions of the ASD user to adopt the VR scenario-based game accordingly. This VR-based training offers a promising therapeutic application for enhancing emotional skills and social interactions in children with ASD.

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I. Introduction

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a multifaceted neurodevelopmental condition that significantly impacts social communication, interaction, and behaviour. Globally, approximately one in 100 children is diagnosed with ASD, which encompasses a broad spectrum of symptoms [1]. Key indicators for diagnosis, as identified by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), include challenges with social responsiveness, difficulty in understanding non-verbal cues, and impaired gestural communication [2]. These difficulties often hinder individuals from recognizing emotions accurately, leading to misinterpretations in social exchange and affecting overall life quality.

The rapid growth of digital health applications has motivated the development of effective digital tools for supporting ASD patients and reducing its impacts. Digital therapy offers innovative solutions for patients and healthcare providers by enabling patient-led care that is more personalized and data-driven. By gathering vital information over time, these tools can facilitate more accurate diagnoses and treatments compared to traditional medical interactions, enhancing the quality, efficiency, and accessibility of care. Moreover, advances in technology, particularly in virtual reality (VR) and gamified learning, provide new approaches for behavioural treatment, particularly for children. This form of treatment can be more acceptable to children as they learn and improve their social interactions skills by playing a VR game. Furthermore, such digital application can reduce the workload of clinicians.

II. Material and methods

This project aims to develop an innovative therapeutic system that can help individuals, in particular children, affected by ASD mitigating the impacts of ASD. The system is based on creating a virtual reality (VR) game designed for training children with ASD to develop emotions and perceive nonverbal cues such as facial expressions during social communications with others.

II.1. VR system overview

The key components for establishing the VR system are illustrated in Fig. 1. The main components of the proposed system are the development of a VR environment suitable to the intended training purposes and artificial intelligence (AI) based approaches for processing and analysing the user data during the gameplay.

Figure 1: The main components of the VR system for training children with ASD.

The VR environment allows users to experience and socially engage in emotion-related scenarios, providing children with ASD an interactive simulation of everyday situations. To establish the required VR environment, scenarios of various situations were defined [3], avatars were created [4] and required objects to build the VR world were designed or imported from the Unity Asset Store.

User data are collected and processed to recognise the user responses and reactions during the gameplay. The data includes user inputs e.g. using VR controllers, physiological data e.g. ECG and facial images [5,6]. By processing the physiological data, user status, such as stress level, can be determined [7]. Moreover, the facial images enable the system to recognise expressions and emotions of the user. To this end, AI models were developed for recognising emotions in facial images [8].

The system analyses the user responses and interactions throughout the game to adapt the VR environment according to the individual status and needs. This adaptation is conducted by providing feedback to the VR environment. At the end of the game, a report is generated allowing clinicians monitoring the treatment and the progress of ASD users.

II.II. VR-based training phases

The behavioural training will be conducted in three phases. Initially, the user is trained to mimic the facial expressions of an avatar. The facial expression of the avatar is adjustable, enabling the avatar to express various emotions at different intensity levels. In this phase, ASD users learn how to recognise and replicate facial cues associated with specific emotions, helping to improve emotional awareness and expression. In the second phase, users participate in a 'mirror training' where they can observe their own facial expressions in a virtual avatar. Real-time feedback is provided throughout both phases, allowing users to refine and adjust their emotional expressions more accurately.

In the third phase of the training, the user engages in a VR game that presents real-life scenarios of varying complexity. Using a virtual tablet within the VR game, the user can select different scenarios. This phase trains ASD users to interact and express appropriate emotions and behaviours in predefined situations, helping them practice emotional responses and social interactions in a safe, controlled environment.

III. Results and discussion

Three version of avatars varying in detail level were created. A study was conducted to evaluate each of these avatars in terms of ability to express emotions and at which intensity level the emotion can be recognised. The findings revealed that simpler avatars were more effective at representing emotions than highly detailed ones. Furthermore, the avatar with moderate detail was found to be the most acceptable and best suited for use in the system [4].

Four scenarios representing various everyday situations were defined. These include relaxed scenarios, such as communicating and interacting with friends. Additionally, challenging real-world situations are incorporated to train ASD users managing more difficult interactions. For

example, one scenario requires the user to return a product to a store and engage with an unfriendly salesperson [3].

A deep learning approach was developed for recognising emotion using the facial images. This approach is based on a graph convolutional network (GCN) that recognises emotions using a mesh generated from facial landmarks. GCN achieved 59% mean accuracy [8].

A study was carried out to evaluate the effectiveness of mimic training. Findings indicated a strong correlation between the facial expressions of an avatar and the user emotions. Users achieved an accuracy of 85% in understanding emotions. Additionally, users successfully mimicked the avatar's expressions with a rate of 47%. These results highlight the potential of this training to enhance emotional understanding and development in individuals with ASD.

IV. Conclusions

The development of a VR-based emotion training system represents a significant advancement in therapeutic approaches for children with ASD. The VR system facilitates the recognition and expression of emotions, essential skills that are often challenging for individuals with ASD. The positive findings from the study indicate that both the avatar designs and the structured training phases contribute effectively to emotional perception. The combination of real-time feedback and scenario-based learning creates a supportive environment for users to practice social interactions.

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